

ҚАЗАҚСТАН РЕСПУБЛИКАСЫ БІЛІМ ЖӘНЕ ҒЫЛЫМ МИНИСТРЛІГІ
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**«Қоғамдық сананы жаңғырту контекстіндегі когнитивті
лингвистика» халықаралық ғылыми-практикалық
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модернизации общественного сознания»
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«Қоғамдық сананы жаңғырту контекстіндегі когнитивті лингвистика» атты халықаралық ғылыми конференция. Материалдары. = «Когнитивная лингвистика в контексте модернизации общественного сознания»: Материалы Междунар. науч.-практ. конф. = Materials of the International Scientific Conference «Cognitive Linguistics in the Context of Modernization of Kazakhstan's Identity» - Алматы, 2018.

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«Қоғамдық сананы жаңғырту контекстіндегі когнитивті лингвистика» атты халықаралық ғылыми конференция материалдары жинағында «Рухани жаңғыру» бағдарламасын жүзеге асыру мәнмәтінінде қоғамдық сананы белсендірудің тиімді жолдарын табу және лингвистиканың когнитивті бағыт аясында қарастырылатын заманауи мәселелердің кең спектрін талқылаумен байланысты тіл мен ойлау ықпалдастығының мәселелері, соның ішінде пәнаралық аспектідегі ғылыми зерттеулер нәтижелері жарық көрген.

В материалах международной научно-практической конференции «Когнитивная лингвистика в контексте модернизации общественного сознания» опубликованы результаты научных исследований, посвященных поиску эффективных путей активизации общественного сознания в контексте реализации программы «Рухани жанғыру» и связанных с обсуждением широкого спектра современных проблем, изучаемых в рамках когнитивного направления в лингвистике, в том числе в междисциплинарном аспекте.

The materials of the international scientific conference «Cognitive Linguistics in the Context of Modernization of Kazakhstan's Identity» are devoted to searching for effective ways to enhance the society public consciousness in the context of the Rukhani Zhangyru program implementing as well as to discussing a wide range of contemporary problems being studied in the framework of the cognitive linguistics.

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THE CAUSES OF THE FIRST ANGLO-AFGHAN WAR

The 19th century was a period of diplomatic competition between the British and Russian empires for spheres of influence in Asia known as the «Great Game» to the British and the «Tournament of Shadows» to the Russians. With the exception of the insane Emperor Paul who ordered an invasion of India in 1800 (which was cancelled after his assassination in 1801), no Russian tsar ever seriously considered invading India, but for most of the 19th century, Russia was viewed as «the enemy» in Britain, and any Russian advance into Central Asia was always assumed in London to be directed towards the conquest of India as the American historian David Fromkin observed «no matter how far-fetched» such an interpretation might be. In 1832, the First Reform Bill lowering the franchise requirements to vote and hold office in the United Kingdom was passed, which the ultra-conservative Emperor Nicholas I of Russia openly disapproved of, settling the stage for an Anglo-Russian «cold war», with many believing that Russian autocracy and British democracy were bound to clash. In 1837, Lord Palmerston and John Hobhouse, fearing the instability of Afghanistan, the Sindh, and the increasing power of the Sikh kingdom to the northwest, raised the spectre of a possible Russian invasion of British India through Afghanistan. The Russian Empire was slowly extending its domain into Central Asia, and this was seen by the East India Company as a possible threat to their interests in India. In 19th century Russia, there was the ideology of

Russia's «special mission in the East», namely Russia had the «duty» to conquer much of Asia, through this was more directed against the nations of Central Asia and the alleged «Yellow Peril» of China than India. The British tended to misunderstand the foreign policy of the Emperor Nicholas I as anti-British and intent upon an expansionary policy in Asia; whereas in fact though Nicholas disliked Britain as a liberal democratic state that he considered to be rather «strange», he always believed it was possible to reach an understanding with Britain on spheres of influence in Asia, believing that the essentially conservative nature of British society would retard the advent of liberalism. The main goal of Nicholas's foreign policy was not the conquest of Asia, but rather upholding the status quo in Europe, especially by co-operating with Prussia and Austria, and in isolating France, as Louis Philippe I, the King of the French was a man who Nicholas hated as an «usurper». The duc d'Orleans had once been Nicholas's friend, but when he assumed the throne of France after the revolution of 1830, Nicholas was consumed with hatred for his former friend who, as he saw it, had gone over to what he perceived as the dark side of liberalism.

The Company sent an envoy to Kabul to form an alliance with Afghanistan's Amir, Dost Mohammad Khan against Russia. Dost Mohammad had recently lost Afghanistan's second capital of Peshawar to the Sikh Empire and was willing to form an alliance with Britain if they gave support to retake it, but the British were unwilling. Instead, the British feared the French-trained Dal Khalsa, and they considered the Sikh army to be a far more formidable threat than the Afghans who did not have an army at all, instead having only a tribal levy where under the banner of jihad tribesmen would come out to fight for the Emir. The Dal Khalsa was an enormous force that had been trained by French officers, was equipped with modern weapons and was widely considered to be one of the most powerful armies on the entire Indian subcontinent. For this reason, Lord Auckland preferred an alliance with the Punjab over an alliance with Afghanistan, which had nothing equivalent to the Dal Khalsa. The British could have had an alliance with the Punjab or Afghanistan, but not both at the same time. When Governor-General of India Lord Auckland heard about the arrival of Russian envoy Count Jan Prosper Witkiewicz (better known by the Russian version of his name as Yan Vitkevich) in Kabul and the possibility that Dost Mohammad might turn to Russia for support, his political advisers exaggerated the threat. Burnes described Witkiewicz: «He was a gentlemanly and agreeable man, of about thirty years of age, spoke French, Turkish and Persian fluently, and wore the uniform of an officer of the Cossacks». The presence of Witkiewicz had

thrown Burnes into a state of despair, leading one contemporary to note that he «abandoned himself to despair, bound his head with wet towels and handkerchiefs and took to the smelling bottle». Dost Mohammad had in fact invited Count Witkiewicz to Kabul as a way to frighten the British into making an alliance with him against his archenemy Ranjit Singh, the Maharaja of the Punjab, not because he really wanted an alliance with Russia. The British had the power to compel Singh to return the former Afghan territories he had conquered whereas the Russians did not, which explains why Dost Mohammad Khan wanted an alliance with the British. Alexander Burnes, the Scotsman who served as the East India Company's chief political officer in Afghanistan wrote home after having dinner with Count Witkiewicz and Dost Mohammad in late December 1837: «We are in a mess here. The emperor of Russia has sent an envoy to Kabul to offer...money [to the Afghans] to fight Rajeet Singh!!! I could not believe my own eyes or ears. On 20 January 1838, Lord Auckland sent an ultimatum to Dost Mohammad telling him: «You must desist from all correspondence with Russia. You must never receive agents from them, or have ought to do with them without our sanction; you must dismiss Captain Viktevitich with courtesy; you must surrender all claims to Peshawar». Burnes himself had complained that Lord Auckland's letter was «so dictatorial and supercilious as to indicate the writer's intention that it should give offense», and tried to avoid delivering it for long as possible.[18] Dost Mohammad was indeed offended by the letter, but in order to avoid a war, he had his special military advisor, the American adventurer Josiah Harlan engage in talks with Burnes to see if some compromise could be arranged. Burnes in fact had no power to negotiate anything, and Harlan complained.

That Burnes was just stalling, which led to Dost Mohammad expelling the British diplomatic mission on 26 April 1838. [1]

British fears of a Russian invasion of India took one step closer to becoming a reality when negotiations between the Afghans and Russians broke down in 1838. The Qajar dynasty of Persia, with Russian support, attempted the Siege of Herat. Herat is a city that had historically belonged to Persia that the Qajar shahs had long desired to take back and is located in a plain so fertile that is known as the «Granary of Central Asia»; whoever controls Herat and the surrounding countryside also controls the largest source of grain in all of Central Asia. Russia, wanting to increase its presence in Central Asia, had formed an alliance with Qajar Persia, which had territorial disputes with Afghanistan as Herat had been part of the Safavid Persia before 1709. Lord Auckland's plan was to drive away the besiegers and replace Dost Mohammad with Shuja Shah Durrani, who had once ruled Afghanistan and who was willing to ally himself with anyone who might restore him to the Afghan throne. At one point, Shuja had hired an American adventurer Josiah Harlan to overthrow Dost Mohammad Khan, despite the fact Harlan's military experience comprised only working as a surgeon with the East India Company's troops in First Burma War. Shuja Shah had been deposed in 1809 and been living in exile in British India since 1818, collecting a pension from the East India Company, which believed that he might be useful one day. The British denied that they were invading Afghanistan, claiming they were merely supporting its «legitimate» Shuja government against foreign interference and factious opposition. Shuja Shah by 1838 was barely remembered by most of his former subjects and those that did viewed him as a cruel, tyrannical ruler who, as the British were soon to learn, had almost no popular support in Afghanistan.

On October 1, 1838 Lord Auckland issued the Simla Declaration attacking Dost Mohammed Khan for making «an unprovoked attack» on the empire of «our ancient ally, Maharaja Ranjeet Singh», going on to declare that Suja Shah was «popular throughout Afghanistan» and would enter his former realm «surrounded by his own troops and be supported against foreign interference and factious opposition by the British Army». As the Persians had broken off the siege of Herat and the Emperor Nicholas I of Russia had ordered Count Vitkevich home (he was to commit suicide upon reaching St. Petersburg), the reasons for attempting to put Shuja Shah back on the Afghan throne had vanished. The British historian Sir John William Kaye wrote that the failure of the Persians to take Herat «cut from under the feet of Lord Auckland all ground of justification and rendered the expedition across the Indus at once a folly and a crime». But at this point, Auckland was committed to putting Afghanistan into the British sphere of influence and nothing would stop him from going ahead with the invasion. On 25 November 1838, the two most powerful armies on the Indian subcontinent assembled in a grand review at Ferozepore

as Ranjit Singh, the Maharajah of the Punjab brought out the Dal Khalsa to march alongside the sepoy troops of the East India Company and the British troops in India with Lord Auckland himself present amid much colorful pageantry and music as men dressed in brightly colored uniforms together with horses and elephants marched in an impressive demonstration of military might. Lord Auckland declared that the «Grand Army of the Indus» would now start the march on Kabul to depose Dost Mohammed and put Shuja Shah back on the Afghan throne, ostensibly because the latter was the rightful Emir, but in reality to place Afghanistan into the British sphere of influence. The Duke of Wellington speaking in the House of Lords condemned the invasion, saying that the real difficulties would only begin after the invasion's success, predicating that Anglo-Indian force would rout the Afghan tribal levy, but then find themselves struggling to hold on given the terrain of the Hindu Kush mountains and Afghanistan had no modern roads, calling the entire operation «stupid» given that Afghanistan was a land of rocks, sands, deserts, ice and snow. [2]

The Afghans Revolted: The Afghan population deeply resented the British troops. Tensions slowly escalated, and despite warnings from friendly Afghans that an uprising was inevitable, the British were unprepared in November 1841 when an insurrection broke out in Kabul.

A mob encircled the house of Sir Alexander Burnes. The British diplomat tried to offer the crowd money to disburse, to no effect. The lightly defended residence was overrun. Burnes and his brother were both brutally murdered.

The British troops in the city were greatly outnumbered and unable to defend themselves properly, as the cantonment was encircled.

A truce was arranged in late November, and it seems the Afghans simply wanted the British to leave the country. But tensions escalated when the son of Dost Mohammed, Muhammad Akbar Khan, appeared in Kabul, and took a harder line. [3]

British Were Forced to Flee: Sir William McNaghten, who had been trying to negotiate a way out of the city, was murdered on December 23, 1841, reportedly by Muhammad Akbar Khan himself. The British, their situation hopeless, somehow managed to negotiate a treaty to leave Afghanistan.

On January 6, 1842, the British began their withdrawal from Kabul. Leaving the city were 4,500 British troops and 12,000 civilians who had followed the British Army to Kabul. The plan was to march to Jalalabad, about 90 miles away.

The retreat in the brutally cold weather took an immediate toll, and many died from exposure in the first days. And despite the treaty, the British column came under attack when it reached a mountain pass, the Khurd Kabul. The retreat became a massacre. [4]

Slaughter in the Mountain Passes of Afghanistan: A magazine based in Boston, the North American Review, published a remarkably extensive and timely account titled “The English in Afghanistan” six months later, in July 1842. It contained this vivid description (some antiquated spellings have been left intact):

«On the 6th of January, 1842, the Kabul forces commenced their retreat through the dismal pass, destined to be their grave. On the third day they were attacked by the mountaineers from all points, and a fearful slaughter ensued...

«The troops kept on, and awful scenes ensued. Without food, mangled and cut to pieces, each one caring only for himself, all subordination had fled; and the soldiers of the forty-fourth English regiment are reported to have knocked down their officers with the butts of their muskets.

On the 13th of January, just seven days after the retreat commenced, one man, bloody and torn, mounted on a miserable pony, and pursued by horsemen, was seen riding furiously across the plains to Jalalabad. That was Dr. Braydon, the sole person to tell the tale of the passage of Khourd Kabul. [5]

More than 16,000 people had set out on the retreat from Kabul, and in the end only one man, Dr. William Braydon, a British Army surgeon, had made it alive to Jalalabad.

The garrison there lit signal fires and sounded bugles to guide other British survivors to safety. But after several days they realized that Braydon would be the only one. It was believed the Afghans let him live so he could tell the grisly story.

The legend of the sole survivor, while not quite accurate, endured. In the 1870s, a British painter,

Elizabeth Thompson, Lady Butler, produced a dramatic painting of a soldier on a dying horse said to be based on the story of Braydon. The painting, titled «Remnants of an Army,» became famous and is in the collection of the Tate Gallery in London.

The Retreat from Kabul Was a Severe Blow to British Pride:

The loss of so many troops to mountain tribesmen was, of course, a bitter humiliation for the British. With Kabul lost, a campaign was mounted to evacuate the rest of the British troops from garrisons in Afghanistan, and the British then withdrew from the country entirely.

And while popular legend held that Dr. Braydon was the only survivor from the horrific retreat from Kabul, some British troops and their wives had been taken hostage by Afghans and were later rescued and released. And a few other survivors turned up over the years.

One account, in a history of Afghanistan by former British diplomat Sir Martin Ewan's, contends that in the 1920s two elderly women in Kabul were introduced to British diplomats. Astoundingly, they had been on the retreat as babies. Their British parents had apparently been killed, but they had been rescued and brought up by Afghan families.

Despite the 1842 disaster, the British did not abandon hopes of controlling Afghanistan. The Second Anglo-Afghan War of 1878-1880 secured a diplomatic solution which kept Russian influence out of Afghanistan for the remainder of the 19th century.

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